

Bacterial Orders

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|------------------|-----------------|---------------|------------------|-----------------|
| Enterobacterales | Xanthomonadales | Opitutales | Flavobacteriales | Mycobacteriales |
| Burkholderiales | Vibrionales | Chloroplast | Micrococcales | Pasteurellales |
| Bacillales | Rhizobiales | Clostridiales | Lactobacillales | Shingomonadales |
| Alteromonadales | Pseudomonadales | Bacteroidales | Fusobacteriales | Neisseriales |
| ■ Others | | | | |

Additional Supplementary Figure: Bacterial composition of removed sequences during contaminant removal and filtering rare taxa procedures. Taxonomic assignments of contaminant sequences (A) and rare sequences (B) that did not comprise at least 0.1% of one or more ant sequence libraries at the bacterial order level across removed blank samples, two removed ant samples (YH100_L04 and YH091_A03), and remained pooled ant samples for each ant colony. Remained ant samples were pooled for each colony and the relative abundance of bacterial orders were averaged for each colony.